

Automated Estimation of Currents from Surfactant Flow in RAR and SAR Imagery Using Projection Pursuit Methods

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Abstract— This paper describes methods which are being developed to automate the detection and tracking of surfactant flow for the purpose of estimating ocean surface currents.

I. INTRODUCTION

While surfactant is usually observable as dark continuous streaks in SAR or RAR imagery, simple thresholding will not separate surfactant image pixels from other pixels under all conditions. Atmospheric fronts and other contaminating phenomena may obscure the surfactant signature by reducing the degree of contrast with the surrounding region as shown in Figure 1. This makes simple thresholding un-

Fig. 1. Small segment of a SIRC L-Band HH Polarization image of the Chesapeake Bay, showing surfactant slicks and atmospheric damping of surface roughness.

reliable, and therefore, our approach uses texture to identify surfactant image pixels even in areas of low contrast.

II. IDENTIFYING SURFACTANT USING TEXTURE

A general approach to texture-based detection of surfactant is first described and demonstrated in a small sample

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of RAR imagery obtained from the Second Coastal Outflow Plume Experiment (COPE-II) [6] (Figure 3). We also describe a means of automatically tracking surfactant pixels as determined by our detection scheme. An illustration of this is provided using SAR imagery obtained from the ONR High-Resolution Field Experiment [5]: In [5], ocean surface currents were estimated from the motion of surfactant slicks identified by a human interpreter in a pair of SAR images from this experiment. The images were separated by a twenty minute interval, and the surfactant masks were correlated to infer the estimated velocity vectors. The approach we describe here fully automates this procedure by replacing the human interpreter with an automated detection system.

The general flow of processing for surfactant detection is described in Figure 2. Our approach begins by representing data windows using a variety of preprocessing techniques such as Gray-Level histograms (GLH), Gray-Level Difference Vector (GLDV) histograms, ratios of such histograms between the whole input box and a sub-region of the box (GLH_RATIO and GLDV_RATIO), or appropriate normalization of the raw pixel intensities. Our approach uses both fixed statistics of the histograms as is done in [2], [3], and [7], as well as the actual histograms. Typically, these representations may be high-dimensional (perhaps several hundreds or thousands of bins). At the next stage of processing, features from each of these representations are extracted by unsupervised (no data labels) feature extraction techniques such as Projection Pursuit (PP) [4] [1] and Wavelet Projection Pursuit (WPP) [1]. Wavelet Projection Pursuit filters are adapted directly to the statistics of the pixels after normalization. The PP and WPP algorithms are used to reduce the dimensionality of the problem and extract statistically interesting information about each representation in a low-dimensional set of projections, which reveal multi-modal data structure.

The final stage of processing involves a generalized non-linear regression between the abstract texture features extracted from each data representation at the previous stage and data labels applied to a set of model-construction data labeled by a human expert. Once the model is constructed, sequestered test images are scanned by the detection model, and a surfactant output probability image

Fig. 2. Automated Detection of Surfactant Pixels in RAR and SAR Imagery.

is generated for each test image; a binary mask at a user-specified threshold is also produced to flag high confidence surfactant regions and further delimit regions of interest where surfactant pixels are likely. This threshold is typically determined from a cross-validation data set.

III. ESTIMATING OCEAN SURFACE CURRENTS BY CORRELATING AUTOMATIC SURFACTANT DETECTION MASKS

In Figure 4, we illustrate the process of estimating current flow once our automated surfactant detection model has been constructed. Surfactant output probability images and binary masks are generated for successive images in a pair of SAR images, coregistered and separated in time, of the ocean surface in a littoral region; a simple correlation search between the output probability images, gated by the binary masks, is used to determine the most likely direction of flow for surfactant slicks in the image. For each window position in the first output probability image, the second is scanned and a correlation measure is obtained; the peak of this correlation matrix determines the most likely direction of flow. The calculated flow vectors are taken as an estimate of ocean surface current.

In one set of experiments, we generated an automatic detection model from a combination of SAR imagery from from the ONR High-Resolution Field Experiment [5] and from SIRC. The combined data set consisted of L-Band, HH Polarization SAR images at 25m and 12.5m resolution. Two sequestered, overlapping images, separated by an interval of 20 minutes, were used to evaluate the ability to detect surfactant and then correlate the results for an automatic estimate of ocean current flow. These are the same two scenes described in [5]. Initial results are shown in Figure 5.

IV. DISCUSSION

The majority of the flow vectors in the area of the Gulf Stream found in the right portion of the images in Figure 5 are consistent with those found in [5]. Our detection system also made some estimate of flow for the surfactant pixels found in the left portion of the image where an atmo-

Initial Results on Novel RAR Test Imagery: Automatic Identification of Surfactant Slicks

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Initial Result: Detection of Surfactant Pixels in RAR COPE-2 Imagery

Fig. 3. Automated Detection of Surfactant Pixels in RAR Imagery from the COPE-II experiment. (Top) Comparison of HH pol RAR sequestered test image with human interpreter's surfactant mask and the output of the automatic detection system. Large shadow in the bottom of the RAR image is due to turning of aircraft. (Bottom) Receiver operating curve for detection of surfactant by the Projection Pursuit detection performance dramatically exceeds simple thresholding scheme (curves use the human interpreter's mask as ground truth).

spheric front has dampened surface roughness. Presently our approach assumes a rigid translation of the surfactant streaks; further improvements could be obtained by allowing for rotation and deformation of the slick features.

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- Does scan box in Binary Surfactant Mask (t) exceed a spatial threshold Δ (sufficient surfactant present to warrant a correlation) ?
- If so, scan in Surfactant Probability Image(t+1) around the position of box in the Surfactant Probability Image (t), calculating the correlation score at each possible location
 - (Correlation score may be gated by the Binary Surfactant Masks at (t) and (t+1) or may use the entire probability field within the box)
- The peak of the correlation matrix yields the estimated flow vector through its association with a particular translation.

Fig. 4. Correlating surfactant detection masks generated by the projection pursuit detection system from successive image frames.

Fig. 5. Automated estimation of ocean surface currents in a pair of SAR images by correlating flow of automated surfactant detection masks.

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